

Electrochemical determination of chitosan based on its supramolecular interaction with thorin

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Abstract : In this paper the diazo dye thorin was selected as a new electrochemical probe for the determination of chitosan (CTS). The electrochemical behavior of thorin with CTS was investigated on a dropping mercury working electrode in 0.2 M Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution (pH 3.7). In B-R buffer thorin could be easily reduced on mercury electrode and showed a sensitive linear sweep voltammetric reductive peak at -0.57 V (vs SCE). In the presence of CTS, the reductive peak current of thorin decreased without the shift of the reductive peak potential and no new peaks appeared, which was due to the formation of a supramolecular complex of thorin with CTS. The binding constant and the binding ratio of thorin with CTS were calculated by the electrochemical data and found to be 1.07×10^9 and 2 : 1, respectively. Under the selected conditions, the decrease in second order derivative linear sweep voltammetric reductive peak current of thorin was in proportion to the CTS concentration in the range 2.5 to 30.0 mg L⁻¹ and the detection limit of CTS was calculated as 1.35 mg L⁻¹ (3 σ). The relative standard deviation (RSD) for 10 replicate determination of 20.0 mg L⁻¹ CTS was 0.79%. Different kinds of samples containing CTS were detected satisfactorily with this method.

Keywords : Chitosan, thorin, supramolecular, interaction, linear sweep voltammetry.

Introduction

Glycosaminoglycans (GAGs), which are composed of repetitive sulphated and/or carboxylated disaccharide units, are important biomacromolecules in the field of biochemistry. In recent years, the particular functions of GAGs in the field of pharmaceutical and biological processes such as cell adhesive, modulation of growth factor activities etc. have aroused great interests¹.

Chitosan (CTS, β -1,4-polyglucosamine) is a kind of natural GAGs with positive charges and has recently attracted much attention from scientists in different fields²⁻⁴. CTS is a linear copolymer of *N*-acetyl-D-glucosamine and glucosamine, with the latter constituting greater than 80% in the molecular structure. It is the product of the partial deacetylation of the naturally occurring polysaccharide chitin, which is found in the exoskeletons of insects and marine invertebrates⁵. CTS has many various desirable properties, e.g. low cost, chemical inertness, low toxicity, high mechanical strength, hydrophilicity, good film forming properties, biocompatibility, biodegradability and anti-bacterial properties^{6,7}. These characteristics make CTS suitable for use in a number of biomedical applica-

tions, including artificial skin, tissue regeneration and drug delivery systems. Numerous processes using CTS to immobilize cells and enzymes had been well-established in various practical fields, e.g. pharmaceutical, environmental and biotechnological applications⁸. There were some articles reporting on the application of CTS to fabricate the modified electrode⁹⁻¹¹, such as CTS modified potentiometric urea biosensor, chitosan-poly(hydroxyethyl methacrylate) modified sulfite biosensor, chitosan-silica gel membrane modified electrochemiluminescence sensor. So it is important to establish a sensitive method for CTS detection. But most of the common methods for CTS detection were based on the indirect spectrophotometry after the acidic hydrolyzation. Gao *et al.*¹² established a spectrophotometric method for the determination of CTS based on the absorbance of zinc-CTS complex at 465 nm. But there are seldom investigations on the determination of CTS by electrochemical methods. In recent years, electroanalysis had been applied to the biomacromolecules determination such as protein¹³, DNA¹⁴ and GAGs¹⁵. Based on the electroactivity of the biomolecule, direct or indirect method has been

devised. If the biomolecule is electroactive, the direct electrochemistry on different kinds of working electrode can be achieved. If the biomolecule is electro-inactive, some electro-active substances can be used as the probe for the indirect detection. For example, Wang *et al.*¹⁶ investigated the electrochemical behavior of Hoechst 33258 and its interaction with DNA by cyclic voltammetry. Sun *et al.*¹⁷ used amaranth as an electrochemical probe for the determination of the proteins such as human serum albumin, bovine serum albumin, bovine haemoglobin and lipase with satisfactory results. Sun *et al.*¹⁸ also applied the light green to determine heparin by linear sweep voltammetry.

In this paper, a simple linear sweep voltammetric method was proposed for electrochemical determination of CTS by using an electroactive dye thorin. In the selected buffer solution, CTS was positively charged and easily interacted with the anionic form of thorin (structure shown in Fig. 1), which resulted in change of electrochemical response. Based on this phenomenon, a new electrochemical method was established for CTS quantification.

Fig. 1. The molecular structure of thorin.

Experimental

Reagents :

A $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ thorin (Shanghai Zhongxin Chemical Company, China) stock solution was prepared by dissolving it in doubly distilled water. 1.0 g L^{-1} CTS (85% deacetylated, Zhejiang Yuhuan Ocean Chemical Company, China) was prepared by dissolving it directly in 1.0% acetic acid solution and stored in the refrigerator at $4 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. A series of $0.2 M$ Britton-Robinson (B-R) buffer solution was used as the reaction medium and the supporting electrolyte. All other reagents were of analytical reagent grade and doubly distilled water was used throughout.

Apparatus :

The second order derivative linear sweep voltammetric determination was carried out on a model JP-303 polarographic analyzer (Chengdu Apparatus Factory, China)

with a traditional three-electrode system composed of a dropping mercury working electrode (DME), a saturated calomel reference electrode (SCE) and a platinum wire auxiliary electrode. The absorption measurement was performed on a Cary 50 probe UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Varian Company, Australia). The pH values were measured with a pHs-25 acidity meter (Shanghai Hongyi Instrument, China). All the experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

General procedure :

2.0 ml of pH 3.7 B-R buffer, 0.6 ml of $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ thorin and an appropriate quantity of CTS solution were added to 10 ml calibrated tube in sequence, diluted to the mark with water and mixed thoroughly. After reaction for 15 min, the second order derivative linear sweep voltammetric curve of the reaction solution was recorded in the potential range from -0.2 V to -1.0 V and the voltammetric peak current (I_p'') were recorded. Under the same conditions the voltammetric peak current (I_{p_0}'') of the thorin solution was obtained and then the difference of peak current ($\Delta I_p'' = I_{p_0}'' - I_p''$) was used to determine the concentration of CTS.

Results and discussion

UV-Vis absorption spectra :

Fig. 2 showed the UV-Vis absorption spectra of thorin in the presence and absence of CTS using $6.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ thorin at pH 3.7 B-R buffer solution and changing the CTS concentration. It can be seen that thorin had a maximum absorption peak at 483 nm (curve 1) and CTS had no absorption (curve 5). After the addition of CTS in thorin solution, the absorption peak value decreased greatly without any shift and an isobestic point appeared at 540

Fig. 2. UV-Vis absorption spectra of CTS-thorin reaction system : (1→4) pH 3.7 B-R buffer + $6.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ thorin + 0.0, 5.0, 20.0, 100.0 mg L^{-1} CTS; (5) pH 3.7 B-R buffer + 20.0 mg L^{-1} CTS.

nm, which indicated that an interaction had taken place in the solution.

Linear sweep voltammogram :

To improve the detection sensitivity, a second order derivative linear sweep voltammetry was used throughout the experiments. Fig. 3 showed the typical voltammograms of CTS-thorin interaction solution. Curve 1 was the voltammogram of B-R buffer solution without any electrochemical response. Curve 2 was that of thorin in pH 3.7 B-R buffer solution without CTS, a well-defined voltammetric reductive peak at -0.57 V (vs SCE) appeared, which was due to the electrode reduction of N=N group in the thorin molecules. Curves 3 and 4 were that of thorin with different amounts of CTS. In the presence of CTS, a decrease of the peak current appeared without the movement of the peak potential. The results indicated that thorin could interact with CTS to form a supramolecular complex. In the selected acidic buffer solution, thorin was in anionic and CTS in cationic forms, so that they could bind together by electrostatic attraction. This resulted in the decrease of free concentration of thorin in solution, and hence the decrease of reductive peak current. The decrease of peak current was related to the increase of CTS concentration. Therefore, thorin served as a new electrochemical probe for CTS determination.

Fig. 3. Second order derivative linear sweep voltammetric curves of thorin-CTS reaction system : (1) 0.2 M pH 3.7 B-R; (2→4) (1) + 6.0×10^{-5} M thorin + 0, 20.0, 25.0 mg L⁻¹ CTS, respectively.

Optimization of the reaction conditions :

The medium pH had great effect on the reductive peak current of thorin and its mixture with CTS. As shown in

Fig. 4, the value of $\Delta I_p''$ reached its maximum at pH 3.7. So pH 3.7 B-R buffer solution was selected in this experiment. In a final 10 ml volume of reaction solution, 2.0 ml of the B-R buffer was enough, and the final concentration of B-R buffer was 0.04 M.

Fig. 4. The influence of pH on the binding reaction with 5.0×10^{-5} M thorin and 30.0 mg L⁻¹ CTS.

To investigate the influence of thorin concentration the thorin concentration was varied from 5.0×10^{-6} M to 1.0×10^{-4} M and the results were shown in Fig. 5. It can be seen that the value of $\Delta I_p''$ increased first and then further decreased with the thorin concentration. When the concentration of thorin was at 6.0×10^{-5} M, the value of $\Delta I_p''$ reached the maximum and was employed in the assay.

Fig. 5. The influence of thorin concentration on the binding reaction with 30.0 mg L⁻¹ CTS in pH 3.7 B-R buffer.

Different addition sequence of B-R buffer, thorin and CTS was tested and the results indicated that the best

addition sequence was B-R buffer, thorin and CTS. The result indicated that the electrochemical coupling made thorin bind to CTS.

The reaction between thorin and CTS occurred rapidly at room temperature. The binding reaction reached its equilibrium after 15 min and remained stable for 2 h. Therefore the reaction system can be used for routine applications.

The instrumental conditions such as the scan rate and the dropping mercury standing time for the assay were also studied. The peak current increased with the increase of potential scan rate within 300 to 600 mV s⁻¹ and the value of $\Delta I_p''$ reached a maximum at 600 mV s⁻¹. When the scan rate was more than 600 mV s⁻¹, the peak shape was deformed. The peak current also increased with the increase of the dropping mercury standing time from 1 to 9 s. When the dropping mercury standing time was more than 9 s, the mercury drop would fall down naturally. So the scan rate and the standing time were selected as 600 mV s⁻¹ and 8 s, respectively.

If the binding reaction is caused by electrostatic at-

Working curve :

Under the optimal conditions, a linear relationship between the decrease of the reductive peak current and the CTS concentration was obtained in the range from 2.5 to 30.0 mg L⁻¹. The linear regression equation was obtained as $\Delta I_p'' (nA) = 707.18C (mg L^{-1}) - 1528.8 (n = 12, \gamma = 0.992)$ and the detection limit was calculated as 1.35 mg L⁻¹ (3 σ). The relative standard deviation (RSD) for 10 parallel determinations of 20.0 mg L⁻¹ CTS was 0.79%.

Influence of coexisting substances :

Under the optimal conditions, a study of the influences of various foreign substances such as metal ions, amino acids etc. on the determination of CTS was carried out and the results were shown in Table 1. It can be seen that most of them had no effects on the detection of CTS, excepting SDS and BSA. This may be due to the absorption of SDS on the surface of mercury electrode, while BSA are positively charged and can also compete the interaction of CTS with thorin.

Table 1. Tolerance of coexisting substances on the determination of 20.0 mg L⁻¹ CTS

Coexisting substances	Concentration (M)	Relative error (%)	Coexisting substances	Concentration (mg L ⁻¹)	Relative error (%)
Cu ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	-4.12	L-Tyrosine	2.0	-4.61
Ca ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	-4.48	L-Leucine	2.0	2.12
Mn ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	-3.33	L-Glutamic acid	2.0	-3.72
Fe ³⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	-3.94	L-Arginine	2.0	-7.55
Zn ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	-2.65	L-Glutamine	2.0	1.50
Mg ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	-4.98	L-Cysteine	2.0	0.75
Sn ²⁺	1.0 × 10 ⁻⁶	-3.54	Glycine	2.0	-1.00
DNA	2.0 mg L ⁻¹	4.53	SDS	2.0	-22.60
Glucose	2.0 mg L ⁻¹	5.07	BSA	2.0	14.80

DNA (deoxyribonucleic acid), SDS (sodium dodecyl sulfate), BSA (bovine serum albumin).

traction, it will be disturbed by the ionic strength. The effect of ionic strength on the formation of the complex of thorin with CTS was studied by the addition of different volume of 1.0 M NaCl into the reaction solution. The results indicated that ionic strength had great effect on the change of peak current, which indicated that the interaction of thorin and CTS was mainly caused by electrostatic attraction. The electrostatic shielding effect of the charges on binding reaction with the increase of Na⁺ concentration was unbeneficial to the formation of CTS-thorin complex.

Analysis of synthetic samples :

Three synthetic samples containing different amounts of amino acids, metal ions and CTS were determined according to the general procedure and the results were shown in Table 2. The results indicated that the proposed method could be easily performed with high accuracy.

Stoichiometry of CTS-thorin supramolecular complex :

According to the method proposed by Li¹⁹, the binding number (*m*) and the equilibrium constant (β_s) of CTS-thorin complex could be calculated by the change of the

Table 2. Determination of CTS in synthetic samples ($n = 5$)

Samples	Coexisting substances	Added (mg L ⁻¹)	Found (mg L ⁻¹)	RSD (%)	Recovery (%)
1	L-Leucine, glycine, Zn ²⁺ , Cu ²⁺	20.00	22.58	3.13	112.90
2	L-Glutamine, L-cysteine, Cu ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺	20.00	22.05	2.58	110.25
3	L-Leucine, L-glutamine, Zn ²⁺ , Mn ²⁺	20.00	21.61	5.38	108.07

*Coexisting substances : L-Leucine, glycine, L-glutamine, L-cysteine : 1.0 mg L⁻¹; Zn²⁺, Cu²⁺, Mn²⁺ : 1.0 × 10⁻⁶ M.

reductive peak current. It was assumed that thorin interacted with CTS only and formed a single complex of CTS- m thorin.

The equilibrium constant is deduced as follows :

$$\beta_s = \frac{[\text{CTS-}m \text{ thorin}]}{[\text{CTS}][\text{thorin}]^m} \quad (2)$$

The following equation can be deduced step by step :

$$\Delta I_{\max} = k C_{\text{CTS}} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta I = k [\text{CTS-}m \text{ thorin}] \quad (4)$$

$$[\text{CTS}] + [\text{CTS-}m \text{ thorin}] = C_{\text{CTS}} \quad (5)$$

Therefore :

$$\Delta I_{\max} - \Delta I = k (C_{\text{CTS}} - [\text{CTS-}m \text{ thorin}]) = k [\text{CTS}] \quad (6)$$

Introducing eqs. (2), (4) and (6) gives :

$$\log [\Delta I / (\Delta I_{\max} - \Delta I)] = m \log [\text{thorin}] + \log \beta_s \quad (7)$$

where ΔI was the difference of peak current before and after the addition of CTS, ΔI_{\max} corresponded to the ob-

served peak current. The value of $m = 2.0$ and $\beta_s = 1.07 \times 10^9$ were deduced, which indicated that a stable 1 : 2 complex of CTS-2 thorin was formed in the selected conditions. As thorin has two O-sulphate groups, under the selected pH 3.7 the anionic form of thorin can easily interact with the cationic form of CTS to form a supramolecular complex. According to the binding ratio obtained above, two thorin molecules may bind to one unit of CTS molecule. So a possible binding reaction mechanism is given in Fig. 6, where R represents for thorin molecule.

Conclusions :

The interaction of thorin with CTS resulted in a biosupramolecular complex formation, which greatly decreased the electrochemical response of thorin at -0.57 V. In pH 3.7 buffer, -SO₃H, -AsO₃H groups in thorin molecular structure were in anionic form due to ionization and CTS in positively charged and hence they could interact to form a supramolecular complex. Based on the

Fig. 6. The possible interaction mechanism between CTS and thorin (R).

tained value when the concentration of thorin was extremely higher than that of CTS. C_{CTS} , $[\text{CTS-}m \text{ thorin}]$ and $[\text{CTS}]$ corresponded to the total, bound and free concentration of CTS in the solution, respectively. From the eq. (7), the relation of $\log [\Delta I / (\Delta I_{\max} - \Delta I)]$ versus $\log [\text{thorin}]$ was calculated and plotted with a linear regression equation as $\log [\Delta I / (\Delta I_{\max} - \Delta I)] = 2.01 \log [\text{thorin}] + 9.03$ ($n = 5$, $\gamma = 0.987$). From the intercept and the

decrease of the peak current, an electrochemical method for micro-determination of CTS was established with the advantages of convenience and sensitivity.

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